

TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES HYBRIDISED WITH SELF-REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

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1 Introduction

Even though carbon fibre composites provide excellent stiffness and strength, they show early damage initiation [1] and a low failure strain in tensile loading. The reason for this brittle behaviour is the low failure strain of the fibres, combined with low transverse and shear strength of fibre bundles or layers. Several strategies have been investigated to overcome this problem. Nanofillers and rubber particles for instance can increase the ductility of epoxy matrices [2] or delay the onset of damage [1], but the improvements in composite brittleness are incremental.

A novel route is proposed in order to obtain a step-change rather than an incremental improvement in the brittleness of fibre-reinforced polymer composites. This will allow a better balance between toughness, on one hand, and stiffness and strength, on the other hand. The proposed route consists of hybridising carbon fibre-reinforced composites with ductile fibres.

Ductile fibre-reinforced composites can achieve high composite toughness [3-6], but only a few of them have been commercially exploited, such as self-reinforced composites (SRC). Two popular production processes for SRCs are hot compaction and co-extrusion. Both processes start with highly drawn polymer tapes, which have high molecular orientation and excellent mechanical properties [7, 8]. In co-extrusion, the starting material is a co-extruded tape, in which the outer layer is made of a lower melting point copolymer. On processing, the co-polymer layer melts and the homopolymer core is maintained [9, 10]. The tapes are woven, stacked and inserted into a hot press at a specific temperature to produce the final sheet.

In hot compaction, a process invented and patented by the university of Leeds [5, 11], only oriented homopolymer tapes are used. During processing, the outer surface of the tapes is selectively melted, with the inner core is maintained. Upon cooling, the melted material recrystallizes to form the matrix [12, 13]. The mono-component nature of the tapes yields a narrow, but commercially usable temperature window to perform hot compaction. If the temperature is too high, the oriented tape loses its molecular orientation and melts. If the temperature is too low, on the other hand, the outer sheath will not melt. The advantage of hot compaction, however, is that molecular continuity is achieved between matrix and tapes, as they both originate from the same tape. This molecular continuity is more limited if co-extruded tapes are used.

Early research efforts focused on self-reinforced polyethylene [11, 14], as drawn polyethylene can easily reach a high stiffness and strength. Later, the focus shifted towards self-reinforced polypropylene (SRPP) [9, 12], as it has a higher toughness, a lower price and a larger processing window [5]. Woven SRPP achieves 3-5 GPa stiffness and 100-150 MPa strength, in combination with a failure strain of 15-20% and an excellent impact resistance. This impact resistance is unique, as it even increases with decreasing temperature [5].

The applicability of SRPP is currently hampered by the limited stiffness and strength. This can be improved by hybridisation, which can be done in three different configuration: interlayer, intralayer and intrayarn (see fig. 1). In interlayer, the mixing of both materials occurs on the layer level, by stacking them on top of each other (see fig. 1a). This is most commonly described configuration in literature, as it is easy and cheap. In the intralayer configuration, the yarns or tapes of both materials are woven together [4], creating a more intimate mixing of both

materials (see fig. 1b). Finally, both materials can be mixed on the fibre level (see fig. 1c). The latter configuration has the most intimate mixing and can be expected to have the best mechanical properties. This configuration is unfortunately difficult to produce and expensive.

Results will be presented for intralayer hybrids of continuous carbon fibre polypropylene (CFPP) with SRPP. The highly oriented PP tapes in SRPP add a tough material to the brittle CFPP. The aim is to maximise the toughening while retaining substantial stiffness and strength. This investigation is focused on tensile behaviour.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The polypropylene (PP) tapes were kindly provided by Propex Fabrics GmbH (Germany). These tapes have a draw ratio between 1:10 and 1:15, a stiffness of 8-10 GPa, and a strength of 500-600 MPa.

The unidirectional carbon fibre polypropylene prepregs were sourced from Toray Europe. The prepregs are 300 μm thick and 55 mm wide, but were slit manually to 2.5 mm width. The fibre volume fraction is 47 vol% and the type of fibres is T700S.

Propex Fabrics GmbH also provided a 20 μm thick PP film. This film has a melting point of 163°C and consists of the same PP grade as the tapes.

2.2 Hand weaving

The PP tapes and CFPP prepreg tapes were woven into hybrid fabrics. Folding of the tapes, which is typical phenomenon in automated tape weaving, was avoided by using a hand loom. The warp direction was composed of only PP tapes, while 1 out of 4 tapes in the weft direction was a CFPP prepreg. This fraction of CFPP prepregs to PP tapes was chosen to give a carbon fibre fraction in the final composite sheet of around 20%.

Two weave patterns were woven to assess the influence of the weave pattern and crimp. To obtain a large difference between both patterns, a plain weave was compared to sateen 8/3 weave (see fig. 2a and 2b). The plain weave pattern has the highest possible crimp of all standard patterns. The sateen 8/3 pattern has a low amount of cross-overs and hence a low crimp. After hot compaction, each layer will have an average thickness of around 150 μm .

A plain weave without carbon fibre prepregs was also woven (see fig. 2c). This will be used as reference material to compare the hybrid composites with.

2.3 Hot compaction

A total of 8 layers of the fabric were stacked on top of each other in a 0_8 or $(0-90-0-90)_8$ layup. The weft direction is labelled as the 0° direction, as this is the stiffest and strongest direction. The layups are abbreviated to 0° and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ respectively. Note that the layup for the reference SRPP fabric is irrelevant, since the 0° and 90° are identical.

The layup is put in between two 1 mm thick copper cover plates and inserted into a preheated press at 188 °C. It is hot compacted for 5 minutes at 45 bar pressure, after which it is cooled down to 40 °C in 4 minutes.

The reference CFPP material was pressed in a copper channel mold to avoid flow at the edges. The processing conditions are the same, apart from a lower pressure. Pressure was lowered to 5 bar to prevent the material from flowing out of the mold, which would misalign the fibres. The higher pressure for the SRPP reference and hybrids is needed to overcome the entropic shrinkage of the PP tapes during hot compaction.

In one layup, seven interleaved PP films were inserted in between the eight hybrid fabrics. Apart from decreasing the carbon fibre volume fraction from 22% to 19%, the films also create more matrix material. This increases the adhesion between the layers and widens the temperature window for hot compaction [15, 16].

2.4 Tensile tests

Quasi-static tensile tests were performed according to ASTM D3039. Tensile samples of 250x25mm were waterjet cut to minimise the damage to the sample edges. The strain was measured by averaging the surface strain using digital image correlation. After the carbon fibre failure, the surface is damaged and the surface strain cannot be measured anymore. To solve this problem, the crosshead displacement is used to calculate the strain after the carbon fibre failure. This correction is accurate due to two reasons. Firstly, the error in this correction is proportional to the load, which shows only a small

variation. Secondly, the correction was verified on samples without damaged surfaces.

The tensile modulus is calculated as the slope between 0.1% and 0.3% strain. The strength is calculated at two different strains: the strain at which CFPP fails and the strain at which SRPP fails. Both these strengths and the corresponding strains are labelled as I and II. These strains and strengths are illustrated in fig. 3.

2.5 Matrix burn off

Matrix burn off tests were performed according to ASTM D2584. The samples are heated in porcelain crucible until the PP matrix ignites. The samples are then inserted into a muffle furnace for eight hours at 450 °C. The fibre weight fraction is calculated based on the sample weight before and after burn off. This is converted into a fibre volume fraction by assuming a density of 1800 kg/m³ and 920 kg/m³ for CF and PP, respectively.

3 Results

3.1 Reference material

The described hybrid composites consist of two components: CFPP and SRPP. Fig. 4 illustrates the tensile diagrams of both reference materials. CFPP demonstrated a high stiffness and strength, but a low failure strain. This is in strong contrast with the low stiffness and strength of SRPP. These lower tensile properties are compensated by the increased failure strain.

3.2 Influence of the layup

Since the weaves only have carbon fibre in the 0° direction, the layup is vital for the mechanical properties of the hot compacted sheets. Therefore, 0° and 0°/90° layups were hot compacted and tested. Their tensile diagrams are presented in fig. 4, while the second and third columns of table 2 summarise the tensile properties.

Both layups demonstrated a distinct CFPP peak at about 1.5% strain, followed by a SRPP tail. The properties in the second part of the stress-strain diagram are hardly affected by the layup. The SRPP seems to remain unaffected by the energy released upon CFPP failure. Both components can be considered as acting independently. This is possible because of a combination of the high SRPP ductility and the well-known low adhesion between CF and PP.

A crucial difference between both layups is the amount of carbon fibre in the tensile direction. The 0°/90° layup only has half of the carbon fibres in the tensile direction compared to the 0° layup. This results in a stiffness difference of a factor two. Based on the carbon fibre volume fraction of 22% and a CF stiffness of 230 GPa, a stiffness of at least 50.6 GPa would be expected for the 0° layup. The measured 33.5 GPa significantly differs from the expected value, however. This difference has two reasons. Firstly, the modulus of CF is typically measured between 0.5 and 0.7% strain, while the composite modulus is measured between 0.1 and 0.3 % strain. The CF modulus increases by about 20% [17] between 0% and 0.7%, which means the expected modulus may be reduced to 40.5 GPa. Secondly, the PP tapes have a high tendency to shrink during processing. This can induce misalignment of the carbon fibres, further reducing the composite tensile modulus. Finally it is interesting to note that the SRPP portion of the tensile stress-strain curve is independent of the layup, supporting the explanation that the two components are acting independently.

The measured data can also be compared to the predicted behaviour for the 0° layup. The tensile diagram of this layup is easier to predict, as it has no carbon fibres in the transverse direction. The prediction is a rule-of-mixtures based on the experimental reference material data (see fig. 4), weighed by their relative volume. This assumes both components behave in parallel and do not interact with each other. CFPP's volume can be estimated by dividing the carbon fibre content of the hybrid composite (22%) by the fibre volume fraction of the CFPP prepregs (47%). This results in a relative ratio of 47% CFPP and 53% SRPP. These ratios are used as weighing factors for the stress-strain diagrams of the reference materials.

Fig. 6 compares the predicted results with the measurements. The CFPP peak is accurately predicted, both for stiffness and strength. However, a large difference is observed after the CFPP failure. The prediction assumes that CFPP stops carrying load, which means the stress falls back to the level of SRPP at that strain. This results in a vertical stress drop to about 15 MPa. The measured stress is, however, higher, which means the carbon fibres are still carrying a part of the load after they are broken. This results in positive deviation from the rule-of-mixtures, which is often referred to as a positive

hybrid effect. This positive effect decreases with increasing strain and disappears at about 12% strain.

A second discrepancy between prediction and measurement is observed around 20% strain. The prediction yields a higher stress level, which means that some damage to SRPP has occurred.

In conclusion, the layup affects the mechanical properties of the hybrid mainly through the orientation of CFPP. The SRPP part of the tensile diagram remains largely unaffected by the layup.

3.3 Influence of the weave pattern

A plain weave is compared to a satin weave to assess the influence of the amount of crimp. The plain weave has more cross-overs, resulting in higher out-of-plane orientation of both the carbon fibres and the PP tapes. Fig. 7 depicts the tensile diagrams of both weave patterns for 0°/90° layups.

No significant differences were found in the stiffness and strength, which means that the crimp is not affecting the behaviour of the carbon fibres. This can be understood from the dimensions of the CF prepregs and PP tapes. The width over thickness ratio is 8 and 50 respectively, resulting in a low crimp for both weave patterns.

Small differences can be observed in the second part of the tensile diagram. The satin weave has a lower strain II and strength II. This part of the tensile diagram is determined by the damage in SRPP. The cross-overs in the weave pattern act as crack stoppers and tend to limit the extent of the CFPP damage. Since the plain weave has more cross-overs, the CFPP failure damages SRPP over a smaller region. This results in higher strain II and strength II for the plain weave. Moreover, the higher number of cross-overs in the plain weave also results in a wavier surface than in the satin weave. The plain weave's wavier surface results in a higher resistance against delamination and a delayed onset of damage.

In conclusion, a plain weave pattern results in more ductile behaviour, while the stiffness and strength remain unaffected.

3.4 Influence of the interleaved film

Interleaved films were inserted between the hybrid fabrics to increase the amount of matrix created during the hot compaction. This increases the

interlayer bonding and hence the resistance against delamination. The tensile diagrams are shown in fig. 8.

The interleaved films slightly improve the strain I and strength I and result in a sharper CFPP peak. The additional matrix improves the compaction quality and improves the bonding. The latter can delay the onset of failure and increases the sharpness of the peak.

The largest difference is observed in the SRPP part of the tensile diagram. The interleaved film increases the strength II, but dramatically decreases the strain II. This can be understood from the difference in adhesion, which determines the extent of the damaged region. In the composite without the films, the adhesion is low, and the damage spreads out over the entire length of the sample. This prevents the strain from localising in a small region and allows SRPP to be strained independently from CFPP. In composites with interleaved films, however, the improved adhesion limits the extent of damaged area, which localises the applied strain over a smaller length. Locally, the ultimate failure strain is reached before the global ultimate failure strain is reached. At the same time, the improved adhesion allows some of the carbon fibres to contribute to the stress even after the first peak. This results in the increased strength II.

In conclusion, the strength of CFPP and the SRPP peak is increased by interleaved films. The failure strain of SRPP is, however, dramatically decreased.

4 Conclusions

Intralayer hybrids of SRPP and CFPP are able to combine the high stiffness and high strength of carbon fibre composites, without losing the ductility of the self-reinforced polypropylene. This results in a novel hybrid material with an interesting balance between stiffness and toughness.

0° and 0°/90° layups were produced and tested. As expected, the stiffness and strength of the 0° layup is twice as high as that for the 0°/90° layup. The ductility of the hybrid composite was not affected by the layup. Improvements compared to the linear rule-of-mixtures were found after the CFPP failure, meaning that the carbon fibres still contribute after they have failed.

TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES HYBRIDISED WITH SELF-REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

Similar mechanical properties are achieved in satin and plain weave patterns. A small difference is observed in the failure behaviour of the SRPP component. That is, the plain weave pattern is less affected by the carbon fibre failure due to the higher number of cross-overs.

The interlayer adhesion is identified as an important parameter to fine-tune the mechanical properties. Interleaved films, which increase the interlayer adhesion, tend to localise the strain after the carbon fibre failure. This increases the stress in the second part of the tensile diagram, but reduces the ultimate failure strain.

Future work will focus on assessing other mechanical properties, such as bending and impact. The influence of the continuous carbon fibres on the thermoformability of the composite will also be investigated.

Fig. 1. Schematic picture of the three hybridisation configurations (a) interlayer, (b) intralayer, and (c) intrayarn.

Fig. 2. The hybrid fabric of PP tapes and CFPP prepreps (a) plain hybrid weave, (b) satin hybrid weave, and (c) reference PP weave.

Fig. 3. A schematic tensile diagram with illustration of the relevant tensile properties.

Fig. 4. Tensile diagrams of the reference materials.

Fig. 6. Comparison between prediction and measurements of 0° plain weave intralayer hybrids.

Table 1. Tensile properties of the reference materials.

	CFPP	SRPP
Stiffness (GPa)	91 ± 5	3.0 ± 0.2
Strain (%)	1.6 ± 0.1	14.3 ± 1.7
Strength (MPa)	1227 ± 70	117 ± 5

Table 1. Tensile properties of the hybrid composites.

Layup	0°	0°/90°	0°/90°	0°/90°
Pattern	Plain	Plain	Satin	Plain
Film	No	No	No	Yes
Stiffness (GPa)	33.5 ± 3.0	16.1 ± 1.7	16.1 ± 2.0	17.8 ± 0.6
Strain I (%)	1.5 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.1
Strength I (MPa)	522 ± 28	245 ± 20	252 ± 11	280 ± 24
Strain II (%)	13.9 ± 0.2	12.1 ± 0.2	10.7 ± 0.6	6.3 ± 3.3
Strength II (MPa)	69.2 ± 4.4	84 ± 2	75 ± 2	92 ± 9

Fig. 5. Tensile diagrams of the 0° and 0°/90° plain weave intralayer hybrids.

Fig. 7. Tensile diagrams of 0°/90° intralayer hybrids in plain and satin weave.

Fig. 8. Tensile diagrams of 0°/90° plain weave intralayer hybrids with and without film.

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